

Coronavirus Disease Research Community – COVID-19

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Title: **Forecast of COVID19 infections, ITALY**

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I have updated the COVID19 infections in Italy on May 20th, publishing the graphs on the following free blogs:

<https://covid19forecast.blogspot.com/>

<https://euocovid19.blogspot.com/>

<https://forbigaio.blogspot.com/>

The same figures are reported here.

ITALY-COVID19 data and forecast of new cases
May 20th, 2020

The main conclusions of this analysis of forecast, with the Verhulst logistic equation are:

- The decrease of the total infections, still in progress, forecasted after the maximum of April 20th, is confirmed.
- The decrease of the new infections, forecasted at the beginning of April, is confirmed.
- The decrease of the new deaths, forecasted at the beginning of April, is confirmed

The main use of these analyses are:

An eventual increase of the total and new infections and of the new deaths, can be promptly monitored by the employment of this approach.